

A New Record of *Eriborus applicitus* Sheng & Sun, 2006 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) Parasitic on *Cossus insularis* (Staudinger, 1892) (Lepidoptera: Cossidae) from Japan

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Abstract *Eriborus applicitus* Sheng & Sun, 2006 is recorded from Japan for the first time. This species is a parasitoid of carpenter moth, *Cossus insularis* (Staudinger, 1892), which is the pest of orchard trees in Japan. Japanese population of this parasitoid is possibly parthenogenetic.

Introduction

The carpenter moth, *Cossus insularis* (Staudinger, 1892), belonging to Cossidae had been treated as a forest pest injuring *Salix* and *Populus* trees until Nakanishi (2005) reported that this moth is the pest of Japanese pear trees. Thereafter the damage of apple and Japanese pear trees due to this moth have increased (Nakamuta *et al.*, 2010). In the

researches on this pest insect, an ichneumonid species was reared from it and the specimens were brought to the author. This species belongs to the genus *Eriborus* of the subfamily Campopleginae. *Eriborus* is known from 55 species in the world and 12 of them have been recorded from Japan (Yu *et al.*, 2012). Though the parasitoid of carpenter moth could not be assigned to any Japanese species previously recorded, it was well adopted to the description of *E. applicitus* described

Figs. 1–5. *Eriborus applicitus* female from Japan. 1, habitus in lateral view; 2, head in dorsal view; 3, head in frontal view; 4, cocoon in lateral view; 5, mesonotum in dorsal view.

Figs. 6 and 8, *Eriborus applicitus* female from Japan; 7 and 9, *E. niger* female from Japan; 6 and 7, propodeum in dorsal view; 8 and 9, ovipositor in lateral view..

from China as a parasitoid of *Cossus insularis*. In this paper, this parasitoid species is newly recorded from Japan.

Materials and Method

Materials used in this paper are deposited in the collection of Ehime University Museum, Matsuyama, Japan. The following specimens of *Eriborus niger* Momoi, 1970 from Ryukyus, Japan were also examined for comparison: 1♀, Kamiya, Amami-Oshima Is., 13. iii. 1988, M. Sato; 1♀, Yuwan-rindo, Yamato-son, Amami-Oshima Is., 10. xi. 2013, H. Ogai; 1♀2♂, Kume-jima Is., vii. 1995, K. Kinjo; 1♀, 24°27'14.60"N 123°01'56.90"E, Gunkan-iwa, Yonaguni-jima Is., 3. v. 2016, H. Ikeda. Images were taken with a Nikon D90 digital camera attached to a Leica MZ16 stereomicroscope or a Nikon Digital Sight DS-Fi1 camera attached to a Leica S8APO stereomicroscope, and edited using Adobe Photoshop® CS6. Morphological terminology mainly follows Gauld (1991).

Eriborus applicitus Sheng & Sun, 2006 (Figs. 1–6, 8)

Eriborus applicitus Sheng & Sun, 2006: 171; Zhang *et al.*, 2015: 253.

Specimens examined. [Honshu] 2♀, Nakayama Town, Yamagata, iv. 2011 (K. Nakamuta), ex. larva of *Cossus insularis* on *Salix* tree on 16. v. 2011; 9♀, Dry riverbed of Sugawa River, Yamagata City, Yamagata, 10. iv. 2012 (S. Ito), ex. *Cossus insularis* on *Salix*; 10♀, 36°00'N 140°07'E, Matsunosato, Kukizaki, Ibaraki, 28. vii. 2000 (Xiong Chen), ex. *Cossus insularis* on *Salix*; 4♀, Matsunosato, Kukizaki,

Ibaraki, em. 21. vii. 1999 (T. Nakashima), Host: Cossidae Gen. sp. [Shikoku] 50♀, Minamishimada-cho, Tokushima City, Tokushima, 25. vi. 2013 (T. Nakanishi), ex. larva of *Cossus insularis* on *Salix* sp.

Cocoon (Fig. 4) cylindrical, 11.9–15.0 mm long and 4.2–5.2 mm wide; yellowish brown to brown in color.

Distribution. Japan (Honshu, Shikoku) **new record**, China.

Remarks. This is the first record of *Eriborus applicitus* from Japan. Among Japanese species of the genus *Eriborus*, this species resembles *E. niger* Momoi, 1970 distributed in Ryukyus in the bigger body size, the black hind femur and the entirely black metasoma (Fig. 1), but can be easily distinguished from the latter by the wide area speromedia of propodeum (Fig. 6) (narrow in *niger* (Fig. 7)), absence of the carina between area superomedia and area petiolaris (Fig. 6) (present in *niger* (Fig. 7)), the hind tibia with median reddish brown band (Fig. 1) (hind tibia entirely black in *niger*), the fore wing with 2r-m as long as M between 2r-m and 2m-cu (2r-m much longer than M between 2r-m and 2m-cu in *niger*) and the evenly upcurved ovipositor (Fig. 8) (apical portion of ovipositor strongly upcurved in *niger* (Fig. 9)).

This species was described based on 16 females and 11 males reared from *Cossus insularis* feeding on wood of *Malus baccata* (L.) Borkh. 1803 (Sheng & Sun, 2006). Though 75 Japanese specimens were also reared from the host, all of them are females. Thus, it is considered that Japanese population of *E. applicitus* is parthenogenetic.

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